

Música oral del Sur

Revista Internacional

Nº 12 Año 2015

ESPAÑÓLES, INDIOS, AFRICANOS Y GITANOS.
EL ALCANCE GLOBAL DEL FANDANGO EN MÚSICA, CANTO Y DANZA

SPANIARDS, INDIANS, AFRICANS AND GYPSIES:
THE GLOBAL REACH OF THE FANDANGO IN MUSIC, SONG, AND
DANCE

CONSEJERÍA DE CULTURA

Centro de Documentación Musical de Andalucía

Actas del congreso internacional organizado por The Foundation for Iberian Music, The Graduate Center, The City University of New York el 17 y 18 de abril del 2015

Proceedings from the international conference organized and held at The Foundation for Iberian Music, The Graduate Center, The City University of New York, on April 17 and 18, 2015

Depósito Legal: GR-487/95 **I.S.S.N.:** 1138-8579

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THE MALAGUEÑAS OF BREVA, ALBÉNIZ, AND LECUONA: FROM REGIONAL FANDANGO TO GLOBAL POP TUNE

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Resumen

La *Malagueña*, conocida mundialmente por las interpretaciones de Roy Clark, Liberace y los Boston Pops, fue una creación del compositor cubano Ernesto Lecuona. La obra de Lecuona conserva bien la esencia de la malagueña folklórica, una variante regional del fandango popularizado por Juan Brevá a finales del s. XIX e inmortalizada en el canon de la música clásica por Isaac Albéniz. Está claro que Lecuona conocía y fue influido por la “Malagueña” para piano de Albéniz y su *Suite Andaluía* donde aparece la obra. Este artículo repasa la historia de la malagueña desde Brevá a Lecuona, para después analizar su impacto en el ámbito de la cultura popular global.

Palabras clave:

Malagueña, Juan Brevá, Isaac Albéniz, Ernesto Lecuona: desde fandango regional a melodía global pop.

Las Malagueñas de Brevá, Albéniz y Lecuona: del fandango regional a la melodía pop global

Abstract

The *Malagueña* immortalized in renditions by Roy Clark, Liberace, and the Boston Pops was the creation of Cuban composer Ernesto Lecuona. Lecuona’s work conveys much of the essence of the folkloric *malagueña*, a regional variant of the fandango first popularized by Juan Brevá in the late 1800s and immortalized in the classical canon by Isaac Albéniz. It is clear that Lecuona was familiar with and influenced by Albéniz’s pianistic *malagueñas*, and his *Suite Andaluía*, in which the famous “Malagueña” appears, owes an obvious debt to Albéniz’s very similar collections of songs and dances. This paper explores the history of the *malagueña* from Brevá to Lecuona, and then examines its impact in the realm of global popular culture.

Key words:

Malagueña, Juan Brevá, Isaac Albéniz, Ernesto Lecuona

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Aaron Clark, Walter " The Malagueñas of Breva, Albéniz, and Lecuona: From Regional Fandango to Global Pop Tune". *Música Oral del Sur*, n. 12, pp. 325-332, 2015, ISSN 1138-8579

This paper is not the culmination but rather the beginning of a research project that I hope will give me a clearer and deeper understanding of the kind of Spanish music that, over almost five decades, has led my faltering footsteps to this point. This journey is not only musicological but also autobiographical; it is personal in a way that nothing else I have investigated is. If this seems self-indulgent, I beg your indulgence in return.

When I was twelve, growing up in Minneapolis, Minnesota, I wanted to play guitar like my heroes George Harrison and Chuck Berry. Chet Atkins soon became a favorite as well, and I took weekly lessons to learn to emulate these idols. My parents encouraged such musical ambitions but apparently preferred a slightly different outlet for them.

One day, in 1964, I urged them to buy me a pair of Jack Purcell tennis shoes, which my friend Valdimar Bjornson counseled me were *de riguer* if I wanted to enter the ranks of the social elite at University Junior High School, where I was newly a student. My parents made a counteroffer: I could have the shoes if I committed to memory the names of the first twenty books of the Bible. This was a very worthwhile assignment, but since my mother and father were Freemasonic Unitarian Universalists and in no way pious, the invitation seemed a bit out of character for them. Anticipating my bewilderment, they were cunning enough to have an alternative at the ready: learn flamenco guitar. This was a *non sequitur* that gave my adolescent brain whiplash. I had no idea what this was and no clue how my parents, having long resided in the land of the *Beer Barrel Polka*, knew of such a thing. I was not interested and sadly concluded that life without Jack Purcell tennis shoes was conceivable after all, even at the expense of my already minimal social standing.

However, nearly two years later I had a Damascene experience when I arrived at my guitar lesson and witnessed my teacher playing what I soon learned was a *malagueña*. Then and there I determined to forsake all else and follow this, as I was utterly transfixed by these deeply stirring sounds. Unfortunately, that was the only such piece my teacher knew, and I

wanted more. As luck would have it, an apostle of flamenco was available nearby to initiate me into this sacred mystery, and his name was Michael Hauser.

Mike had a degree in forestry from the University of Minnesota and was working in West Africa when he heard the siren song of *cante jondo* and moved to Madrid to study with the legendary flamenco guitarist Luis Maravilla (1914-2000). He had recently returned from an extended residence in Spain when I contacted him for lessons. Over the next four years, Mike imparted to me a treasure trove of great music: *peteneras*, *alegrías*, *bulerías*, *sevillanas*, *soleá*, *tientos*, *tarantas*, *siguiriyas*, *granainas*, *danza mora*, *guajiras*, and more. Also living in Minneapolis at that time was a Spanish woman named María Fernanda, who had danced with Antonio's company before following her American husband to Minnesota. She performed locally with Mike and taught dance classes, which I had the good fortune to accompany.

I also studied flamenco dance, so that I could become a better accompanist; however, these classes I took with George Bonnarens, a U.S. Army veteran who had fought in the Battle of the Bulge and then stayed on after the war to study ballet and Spanish dance in Paris. At the same time, I took lessons in classical guitar with local virtuoso Jeffrey Van and developed a rapport with masterworks from five centuries of Spanish music (a fellow

Figure 1: Photo of the George Bonnarens Flamenco Dance Troupe performing Sevillanas, Minneapolis, Minnesota, 1969 (author second from right).

student of Van at that time was a gifted and promising young virtuosa named Sharon Isbin). Among the guitar transcriptions I learned was *Rumores de La Caleta*, a *malagueña* for piano by Isaac Albéniz.

This was a very enriching education and made the arctic winters of Minnesota bearable. Indeed, it never ceases to amaze me that there was this remote outpost of Spanish traditional culture in a land where winter punished with snowdrifts as high as an elephant's eye and summer tormented with mosquitoes the size of hummingbirds. The lure of flamenco was more powerful than any climatic or entomological adversity and attracted a following as dedicated as it was eccentric: mostly a diverse assortment of office workers, itinerant laborers, housewives, and students. Looking back, I now realize just how fortunate I was to grow up in such a place and time, with such fellow travelers—and with such parents.

Fast forward to the 1990s, after I had finished my dissertation on the operas of Albéniz and was immersed in writing a life and works of the great Spanish composer, for Oxford University Press. Now I had to come to real grips with his piano music, and this led me to a closer examination of his *Recuerdos de viaje*, T. 72,¹⁾ a collection of salon-style nationalist piano pieces from the late 1880s in which “*Rumores de La Caleta (Malagueña)*” appeared. Of course, this was not the only *malagueña* Albéniz ever wrote. He also composed the hauntingly evocative “*Malagueña*” for his *España: Seis hojas de álbum*, T. 95, published in London in 1890, and several of his other Spanish essays clearly evoke the *malagueña*, even if they are not so labelled. His last great work, *Iberia*, T. 105, features a movement entitled “*Málaga*.” In fact, the eminent Albéniz authority Jacinto Torres believes that most of Albéniz's Spanish-style essays basically reduce to the *malagueña*, whether so labeled or not. “*Todo es una malagueña*,” he once declared to me. But the question still looms: why?

One work I became familiar with at this time was his *Rapsodia española* for piano and orchestra, T. 16. The fourth of its five sections is entitled “*Malagueña de Juan Breva*.” It was composed in 1886 and premiered in Madrid the following year. Here was a vital clue to the wellspring of Albéniz's *inspiración malagueña*, namely, Juan Breva. For Breva was from Vélez-Málaga, a few miles to the east of Málaga, where there is a monument to him today. No doubt Albéniz heard Breva perform in Madrid, but he may also have gained direct exposure to the *malagueña* and perhaps Breva himself during his youth and early

¹⁾ T. numbers stand for Torres and derive from the magisterial work by TORRES MULAS, Jacinto, *Catálogo sistemático descriptivo de las obras musicales de Isaac Albéniz*, Madrid: Instituto de Bibliografía Musical, 2001, ISBN 8460728544. Two works by the current author may also be of interest: *Isaac Albéniz: Portrait of a Romantic*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002, ISBN 0199250529; and *Isaac Albéniz: A Research and Information Guide*, New York: Routledge, 2015, ISBN 9780415840323. This latter book contains a catalog of works largely based on Torres's research.

adulthood, as Albéniz made concert appearances in Málaga in 1872, 1882, and again in 1886.²⁾ Málaga was actually a breeding ground not only for the *malagueña* but also for several important flamenco artists.

Juan Brevia's actual name was Antonio Ortega Escalona. Not a Gypsy, he was born in 1844 and died in Málaga in 1918. He is considered one of the great *cantaos* in the history of flamenco, and certainly one of the leading flamenco performers the province of Málaga ever produced. He was a popularizer not only of *malagueñas* but also *verdiales*, a related style of fandango that hailed from the *montes* north of the city. Brevia not only sang but also wrote lyrics and accompanied himself on the guitar. In the opinion of Donn E. Pohren, "Initiated by Juan, the *malagueñas* swept the country, and soon there were more specialists in *malagueñas* than in any other *cante*."³⁾

The *malagueña* that Brevia popularized among aficionados and that Albéniz first familiarized classical connoisseurs with was a type of fandango from Málaga, among the so-called Cantes de Levante. Like much of Spanish traditional folklore in the nineteenth century, it underwent a gradual transformation in the setting of the *café cantante*, where patrons heard their favorite types of song and dance interpreted mostly by Gypsies. Though once danced like other fandangos, especially the *verdiales*, the *malagueña* gradually metamorphosed into a *cante* with guitar accompaniment. In a very loose triple-meter *compás*, it is a *cante libre*, and the voice features the sorts of melismas and microtones one expects in flamenco singing. It is in the E or "Andalusian" mode and emphasizes the chords E major, F major, and G major. The *copla* features excursions to C major, with subdominant and dominant chords, but the music always collapses back into the E mode. The sort of *malagueña* evoked by Albéniz and later composers clearly exhibits both *coplas* in free rhythm and sections in stricter rhythm meant to suggest a guitarist's *falsestas*, or virtuosic solo passages, derived from the kind of music that would earlier have accompanied dancing in the folkloric fandango.⁴⁾ In the twentieth century, the free-rhythm style of *malagueña* became dominant.

This is where we introduce another major player in this unfolding drama, and that is Ernesto Lecuona y Casado, who was born in Havana in 1895 and died in 1963, after fleeing Castro's Cuba for the U.S. He was a virtuoso pianist and a prolific composer of over 600 works, among them the *Suite Andaluía* of 1928, which consists of "Córdoba/Córdoba," "Andaluía/Andaluza," "Alhambra," "Gitanerías, Guadalquivir," and

²⁾ Consult the Albéniz Research and Information Guide, op. cit., pp. 3, 5, 73, and 113, for more information on Albéniz's connections with Málaga.

³⁾ POHREN, Donn E., *Lives and Legends of Flamenco*, Madrid: Society of Spanish Studies, 1988, ISBN 8485042034, p. 51, part of a biographical portrait, pp. 50-54.

⁴⁾ Pohren, op. cit., maintains that Brevia's *malagueñas* exhibited the liveliness of the *verdiales*, which would not only explain their accessibility but also the way they were mimicked in Albéniz's music.

the immortal “Malagueña.” Listening to this suite, it seems clear to me that Lecuona was intimately familiar with Albéniz’s similar collections of pieces inspired by the Spanish south. Not only did Lecuona undoubtedly know Albéniz’s music, but he also traveled to Spain already in 1924, so he had direct experience of the regions and folklore he evoked in his music. Indeed, other Spanish-style piano works by Lecuona included *Ante El Escorial*, *Zambra gitana*, *Aragonesa*, and *Valencia mora*.

Now, one might be suspicious of a *malagueña* composed by a Cuban, but even ultra-purist Donn E. Pohren admitted that Lecuona’s little masterpiece conveys “certain faint traces of a flamenco style,”⁵ though he may have been damning by faint praise. We could argue about just what has made this piece so popular. Perhaps its modality has an appeal that is both exotic and passionate. Perhaps its lively rhythms are catchy. Perhaps its alternation of sections in strict rhythm with those in freer rhythm and suggestive of the *copla* provide attractive variety. Indeed, the composer himself fitted his piece out with lyrics in Spanish.

One thing we cannot dispute is its popularity, whatever the reasons for that may be. It is virtually impossible for a sentient being to pass many years on this planet without hearing the sounds of Lecuona’s *Malagueña*. For many decades now, it has proven to be an evergreen favorite with pianists, guitarists, jazz bands, marching bands, drum-and-bugle corps, and symphony orchestras. And it has been sung not only in Spanish but also English and even German! Pop performers who have popularized Lecuona’s *Malagueña* include Liberace, Bill Haley & His Comets, Roy Clark, José Feliciano, Connie Francis, Carlos Montoya, and Stan Kenton—not to mention the Trashmen and the Bambi Molesters. Figure skaters Sasha Cohen and Kristi Yamaguchi have used this music in their routines, and Yamaguchi won Olympic gold with it in 1992.⁶

Clearly the basic musical ingredients of *Malagueña* have formed a sort museme, or musical meme, that has gone viral in representing Spain and Spanish culture, in a way rivaled only by Bizet’s *Carmen*. We lovers of flamenco can only marvel that the most widely recognized and enduringly popular manifestations of this art form were composed by a Cuban and a Frenchman. But those manifestations could not exist without the real thing to begin with, and for me, at least, flamenco itself possesses an allure that even Lecuona’s *Malagueña* cannot match.

⁵ POHREN, Donn E., *The Art of Flamenco*, 4th rev. ed., Shaftesbury, Dorset: Musical New Services, Ltd., 1984, ISBN 0946570027, pp. 125-26.

⁶ See the remarkably informative Wikipedia entry on Lecuona’s *Malagueña*, [http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Malagueña_\(song\)](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Malagueña_(song)) (accessed April 1, 2015).

Because the day I witnessed my teacher playing a *malagueña* in 1966, it was in fact an arrangement of Lecuona's miniature masterpiece. In fact, American culture in the 1960s was absolutely awash in Lecuona's *Malagueña*, a fascination that was part of a larger trend of flamencophilia evidenced by the popularity of Carlos Montoya, Sabicas, Juan Serrano, the Romero Guitar Quartet, and José Greco. This helps to explain why even my parents were familiar with flamenco. But Lecuona's *Malagueña* would be the portal through which I entered a wider and infinitely more varied world of flamenco itself.

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